

Synthesis of New polycyclic Hetero-Aromatic Hydrocarbons and their photophysical studies

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Synthesis of polycyclic hetero-aromatic hydrocarbons (PHAHs) and elucidate their solid state structures in crystals. The synthesis fully here is simple and provides easy access to this important class of materials.¹One of the most frequently used methodologies for this purpose is the aromatic framework of PHAHs to improve their physicochemical properties and enhance the carrier transport of the system for applications as organic field-effect transistors.²We have designed and synthesized a new family of PHAHs containing a tetracene core which can be synthesized from aldehydes using a various – steps such as sequence of McMurry coupling, Diels – Alder reaction and scholl reaction oxidative aromatization under mild conditions to give final product.

Keywords: Polycyclic hetero-aromatic hydrocarbons, Organic Field-effect Transistors, and Tetracene

References

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